

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Nitrate reductase (NRase) activity as an index for early maturity

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Studying parents and hybrids increases understanding of the nature of the gene action involved in the expression of NRase activity and earliness. NRase is the enzyme involved in converting nitrite to nitrate. We estimated NRase at five stages in four early (IR50, Co 37, ADT37, and ASD16) and five very early rice varieties (ASD8, ASD17, Co 39, Heera, and Kalyani II) and their 20 (5 × 4) hybrids (Table 1).

NRase analysis was carried out using leaf samples following the method of Nicholas et al (1976) at 15, 30, 50, 70, and 90 d after sowing (DAS). The experiment was laid out in randomized block design, with three replications, and conducted at Coimbatore in 1990 wet season (WS) under irrigated condition.

Growth duration of early parents was 105-120 d and 86-95 d for the very early parents. NRase activity increased from seedling to flowering stage (up to 70 DAS) and declined thereafter. NRase increased in late-maturing parent Co 37, but at a rate less than that of early-maturing parents (Table 1). Among the hybrids, ASD16/Kalyani II and IR50/Co 39 recorded very high NRase activity from seedling to flowering stage. Both had durations of 94 d.

All the hybrids were significantly early compared with mean duration of the parents. Most of the hybrids with very early parents Co 39 and Kalyani II matured early. Kalyani II hybrids were the earliest of the F₁s.

Table 1. NRase activity (μ moles NO₂/g fresh weight per h) at different growth stages of varieties and hybrids with different growth durations. Coimbatore, India, 1990 WS.

Variety or hybrid	Duration (d)	15 DAS	30 DAS	50 DAS	70 DAS	90 DAS
IR50	105	1.58	3.12	6.85	8.97	8.43
Co 37	120	1.26	2.77	6.52	8.63	9.14
ADT36	114	1.39	2.93	6.66	8.75	8.76
ASD16	110	1.43	2.96	6.69	8.81	8.72
Co 39	95	1.80	3.34	7.06	9.18	5.23
ASD8	87	1.94	3.45	7.21	9.33	5.94
ASD17	95	1.79	3.32	7.06	9.18	5.81
Heera	87	1.96	3.48	7.23	9.34	5.93
Kalyani II	86	1.99	3.52	7.26	9.38	5.52
Mean of parents	99.89	1.68	3.21	6.95	9.05	7.05
CV (%)	-	16.30	8.52	3.98	3.11	23.33
IR50/Co 39	94	1.82	3.36	7.08	9.26	5.97
IR50/ASD8	105	1.57	3.11	6.81	8.94	8.65
IR50/ASD17	97	1.75	3.28	7.01	9.13	7.47
IR50/Heera	102	1.65	3.18	6.51	9.03	8.25
IR50/Kalyani II	95	1.80	3.33	7.07	9.18	5.77
Co 37/Co 39	112	1.41	2.94	6.67	8.79	8.76
Co 37/ASD8	111	1.49	3.02	6.75	8.87	8.73
Co 37/ASD17	103	1.63	3.02	6.89	8.99	8.27
Co 37/Heera	105	1.59	3.13	6.86	8.98	8.35
Co 37/Kalyani II	94	1.79	3.33	7.06	9.18	5.75
ADT36/Co 39	95	1.77	3.30	7.05	9.16	7.22
ADT36/ASD8	105	1.79	3.32	7.05	9.15	8.33
ADT36/ASD17	101	1.67	3.20	6.53	8.56	8.22
ADT36/Heera	102	1.66	3.19	6.93	9.04	8.26
ADT36/Kalyani II	95	1.80	3.33	7.06	9.18	5.78
ASD16/Co 39	95	1.80	3.32	7.07	9.18	5.77
ASD16/ASD8	95	1.77	3.30	7.03	9.16	7.44
ASD16/ASD17	100	1.69	3.22	6.95	9.06	7.49
ASD16/Heera	106	1.51	3.06	6.76	8.91	8.63
ASD16/Kalyani II	94	1.82	3.35	7.08	9.56	8.65
Mean of F ₁ s	100.30	1.69	3.21	6.91	9.08	7.44
CV (%)	-	7.10	4.04	2.66	2.47	16.06

Table 2. Correlation coefficient between total growth duration and NRase activity at different growth stages. Coimbatore, India, 1990 WS.^a

	15 DAS	30 DAS	50 DAS	70 DAS	90 DAS
Total growth duration	-0.97**	-0.96**	-0.85**	-0.84**	0.87**
15 DAS		0.99**	0.87**	0.86**	-0.84**
30 DAS			0.86**	0.85**	-0.85**
50 DAS				0.89**	-0.81**
70 DAS					-0.81**
90 DAS					

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

Growth duration of the parents and hybrids and NRase activity at 15 DAS showed a significant negative correlation (-0.97** to -0.84**), except for NRase and 90 DAS, which showed a significant positive value (0.87**) (Table 2).

The intercorrelation of NRase activity at different DAS showed significant positive values. Estimating NRase activity seems to be a useful measure for selecting the early-maturing types at an earlier stage of crop growth. ■